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CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AFTER THE PANDEMIC CRISIS IN THE MUNICIPAL SCHOOL SYSTEM OF THE CITY OF SÃO PAULO

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ABSTRACT

The lack of initial teacher training in the development of strategies to promote collaborative human relationships has genuine opportunities in the continuing training of collective teacher study hours to deconstruct inadequate conceptions, develop cooperative practices and give new meaning to one's own experiences. Having overcome adversities directly linked to the acute phase of the Covid-19 pandemic, I have identified four dimensions that are essential to professional practice today: managing anxieties and uncertainties, devising viable strategies for this new context, improving collective collaborative work and managing relationships in the online and face-to-face environment. The aim of this article is to contextualize the importance of building learning through the exercise of students' protagonism, autonomy and determination, given in the dialogue between them and the teacher, in a multi-way learning process with competent mediation. Using the social experiences of the group of students as clues for selecting approaches, content and strategies makes it possible to add meaning for them. Welcoming the vision of the local community into the classroom as a safe starting point enables teaching that is less content-oriented and more focused on comprehensive education (WEISZ, 2009), as well as the use of resources that enable authorial and collaborative production.

Keywords: education; learning; teacher training; didactics; teaching practice

INTRODUCTION

The anguish of discovering that the details of a classroom routine went far beyond the annual planning and preparation of an activity, or any lesson for that matter, highlighted my poor initial teacher training in developing strategies to promote collaborative human relationships. However, the determination to overcome such discomfort and frustration served as fuel for the search for alternatives that, while alleviating the suffering of the uncertainties of the teaching and learning process, would also provide successful experiences for the students.

I found genuine opportunities to deconstruct inadequate conceptions, develop cooperative practices and give new meaning to my experiences as a student and daughter of a public school teacher, experiences permeated by the specificities of black, poor and peripheral women, like my mother and me.

Currently, having overcome adversities directly linked to the acute phase of the Covid-19 pandemic, a historical and atypical planetary moment, in which social distancing and the demands of remote teaching have led me to reflect on my teaching training path, I identify four dimensions that are indispensable to my professional performance today: the management of anxieties and uncertainties, the elaboration of viable strategies for this new context, the improvement in collaborative collective work and the management of relationships in the online and face-to-face environment.

DEVELOPMENT

Reflecting on the functioning of the Brazilian school system prior to the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education No. 9394/96 (BRASIL, 1996), and its amendment via Law No. 10639/2003 - which instituted in the official curriculum the compulsory presence of the theme "Afro-Brazilian and African History and Culture" (BRASIL, 2003) - was the foundation of the continuing education that favored my awareness in welcoming the expectations of boys and girls in the classroom.

The laws and decrees of the colonial and imperial periods did not make significant investments and

efforts to educate the entire population. The 1824 Constitution of Empire Brazil declared that primary education was free for all Brazilian citizens, but excluded enslaved black people from citizenship. Thus, since they were prohibited by the state from having access to school, "the 1872 census revealed that among 1,509,403 enslaved people, only 1,403 knew how to read and write, in other words, less than 1%. The access and integration of the enslaved into society was blocked, preventing them from facing the new challenges of the free wage labor market" (SÃO PAULO, 2008, p.67).

Although paid for by everyone's taxes, in the 1960s we found public schools that were still segregated, neglecting black students and repeatedly promoting the threat of failure as the only way to force children and teenagers to study; a public school that, not built for everyone, required passing competitive entrance exams, blocking and discouraging a significant portion of the student population, especially the most precarious in terms of their financial situation and the establishment of study routines (Weisz, 2009). Child labor, women's role as caretakers of the home and family, and the country's slave-owning past are some of the factors that determined why almost entire segments of society were prevented from accessing school or coerced into dropping out (SÃO PAULO, 2008).

With the 1971 LDB, the separation between primary and secondary schools was eliminated, the entrance exam was abolished and education up to the 8th grade became compulsory. The educational policy aimed to guarantee access to school for the entire population, but the educational system did not direct its strategies towards guaranteeing learning and progression (WEISZ, 2009).

The state, despite being a benefactor in providing a wide range of enrollments, was complicit in maintaining the culture of failure as the only device capable of ensuring quality education, failing to invest in public policies and teacher training that would guarantee adequate teaching and learning processes with equity. In other words, making it possible to access education as a human right, meeting the needs, differences and asymmetries of the various social segments (CHAUÍ, 1995).

So we have compulsory schooling, but far from this meaning that it is for everyone. Government policies

still persist today that are impregnated with this elitist vision of education that is structurally hierarchical and authoritarian, “preserving the marks of colonial slave society” (CHAUI, 1995, p. 74). Weisz (2009) observes that in this scenario, historically characterized by this exclusionary and meritocratic interpretation, the belief that school failure had its origins in malnutrition gained momentum, leading successive governments to expand school lunch programs. Although the importance of healthy eating for the development of life is unquestionable, the use of school feeding policies has not resulted in overcoming educational failure.

Class stereotypes and prejudices, cultivated during successive centuries of denial of the right to humanity, dignity, citizenship and subjectivity, have produced school failure in the daily life of hierarchical and authoritarian relationships in school spaces. Patto (1987) argues that, precisely because of the influence of personal and family history on the trajectory of schooling in Brazilian society, school failure is a psychosocial process, in which students are stigmatized because of their ethnic heritage, social and cultural conditions.

According to Weisz (2009), it was the understanding of the economic role of education in the country’s development that fundamentally changed the way Brazilian society looked at the issue of education. The growing concern with citizenship issues, fostered by social participation, put pressure on Brazilian elites to realize that the traditional exclusion of large population groups from access to basic social welfare conditions would turn against them in two ways: companies needed a consumer market to become more competitive, including abroad, and repeated processes of exclusion would eventually fuel population uprisings.

After an intense process of debate, seeking to reconcile the interests of the various groups representing society, in 1996 the National Congress decreed a new National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (BRASIL, 1996).

At that time, I began my career having contact with colleagues who were confused about how to

reconcile the ideas of universal access to school and making continuous progression within cycles real in the classroom, guaranteeing learning (Weisz, 2009).

In the collective teaching study hours, we clashed with our cultural beliefs countless times, reading texts that intended to expose the tricks of exclusion established in the network of human relationships that are the foundation of this country and, at the same time, deconstruct our conceptions of students, teachers and assessment. Also at the end of the 1990s, the Ministry of Education and Culture’s (MEC) program offered a methodological reference for in-service teacher training. Called PCN em Ação (PCN in Action), it helped to understand the theoretical frameworks of the Parâmetros Curriculares Nacionais (BRASIL, 1999) - the aforementioned PCNs - institutional documents with recommendations on curriculum, drawn up between 1995 and 1998. With national reach, other actions by the MEC addressed the difficulty teachers had with literacy, producing a specific program to train literacy teachers, known as PROFA. This project consisted of offering a permanent training course, based on respect for the group’s knowledge and problem-solving methodologies, written and videographic materials. I was studying for a degree in Languages and Literature and both the teachers from the academy and those who worked with me in the Municipal Education Network of the City of São Paulo (RME) were promoting discussions about developing educational practices that were different from what had been commonly done in the classroom until then.

In 2006, the Municipal Department of Education of the City of São Paulo (SME/SP) implemented the Ler e Escrever Program which, in addition to providing the Literacy Teacher’s Planning Guide, was structured around the ongoing training of pedagogical coordinators (PC) - together with the Technical Guidance Department of the Municipal Department of Education (DOT/SME). The PTs had the task of organizing collective working hours with the teachers and monitoring their pedagogical activities (SÃO PAULO, 2006a).

Expanding the reference material for teacher

improvement, 2007 saw the publication of the document *Orientações Curriculares e Proposição de Expectativas de Aprendizagem* (2007), which was part of the Programa de Orientação Curricular do Ensino Fundamental (Elementary School Curriculum Orientation Program), with the aim of contributing to reflection and discussion in the process of selecting and organizing content.

The document was drawn up based on contributions from specialists in the areas of knowledge and coordinated by the DOT/SME, followed by reading by groups of teachers, supervisors and representatives of the Education Coordinating Offices for the necessary adjustments. This was followed by the curricular reorientation stage, which sought to link the document to the results of external assessments in order to draw up teaching plans that were appropriate to the students' learning needs, prioritizing the provision of social reading and writing practices. The documents *Orientações Curriculares do Ensino Fundamental I*, *Orientações Curriculares do Ensino Fundamental II* (for the areas of knowledge) and the *Referencial de Expectativas para o Desenvolvimento da Competência Leitora e Escritora no Ciclo II do Ensino Fundamental* (2006b) present the term "learning expectations" as development goals, i.e. competences and skills that expand as they are achieved and progressively deepened, in line with the students' development process.

For sometime now, I have been assigned exclusively to the classes as a Reading Room Guidance Teacher (POSL), and I have seen various practices and routines already consolidated by the "reading teachers" (as POSLs are commonly known in the school community) officially recorded in the aforementioned collection. With no obligation to record grades or concepts, the work carried out in the Reading Rooms and Reading Spaces has the primary objective (SÃO PAULO, 2019):

to awaken students' interest in reading, through the experience of various situations in which its use is necessary, and through interaction with published materials from the most diverse literary genres and media, enhancing the

development of reading behavior.

Investing in strategies, time, care and affection in the development of reading behavior (in the most diverse classes, with conflicting profiles and careful preferences) requires POSL professionals to be constantly updated and to have a keen sense of how to involve students who are sometimes disrespected in their right to comprehensive learning.

In this project, the content includes not only objective strategies for the acquisition of students' reading and writing skills, but also strategies that promote self-knowledge and self-care, the improvement of autonomy and determination, conflict mediation, and the management of anxieties and uncertainties. These strategies, which were then organized and documented, became accessible and, above all, indispensable in text production and reading comprehension practices, that is, in the social use of reading and writing in all areas of knowledge (SÃO PAULO, 2006).

In my experience with children, teenagers, young people and adults in the different dynamics of the Reading Room, I met students who were involved in the activities on offer, even though they had a history of low academic performance and indiscipline. My strategies for managing my anxieties, difficulties and uncertainties often also became content, alongside the strategies exemplified by the students themselves and other teachers.

Even more dissatisfied with the lack of progress of some students in regular classes and devoting special attention to trying to understand what was preventing children and adolescents from learning, in 2016 I accepted the proposal to join the Pedagogical Support Project - Parallel Recovery (PAP), starting to attend small classes in the after-school hours in learning recovery workshops.

The PAP's ongoing training is based on the Learning Rights related to the Social Quality of Education. The institutional publication *Learning Rights in the Interdisciplinary and Authorial*

Cycles (2016), emphasized learning as a human right, reflecting the curricular movement National Pact for Literacy at the Right Age (PNAIC) (collaborative agreement signed between the Federal Government, Federal District, States and Municipalities in 2012, to make literacy effective for all children by the end of the 3rd year of elementary school at the latest) (BRASIL, 2017).

In the process of implementing the São Paulo City Curriculum, in 2016 a collection of guiding documents was produced through data collection, action and discussions fostered in working groups (WG), which involved the representation of various segments of the municipal school community. With integral education, equity and inclusive education as their guiding concepts, these collective productions currently make up a collection for the continuing education of RME professionals, as well as being freely accessible to society. In particular, the collection Didactic Guidelines for the City Curriculum brings together relevant notes and suggestions so that planning can find its full functionality in the teaching and learning process, especially in everyday classroom work.

I didn't find in any of these publications, most of which were produced with the collaboration of professionals from the public education system, any justification for school failure based on the family, the one that doesn't stimulate, feed or take proper care of their babies, children and adolescents, although the common justification for low school performance is still concentrated in families in the most precarious situations.

In the classrooms, in the reading circles and in the PAP workshops, I met a number of girls and boys who were restless and questioning, rebellious and savvy, whose way of being and existing in the world caused discomfort and sometimes broke with the school plan. It's human and perfectly acceptable that failure to comply with a plan can cause anguish, but there are ways to make the process of realigning the path part of the plan's success. Pedagogical work requires planning, knowledge, very sharp criteria and intentionality, precisely because of the need to manage the most

uncertainties and anxieties. However, they are natural and permanent in human existence and are also sources of learning (PASCUAL, 2020).

In times of pandemic, the classroom, whether remote or face-to-face, has been a meeting of people full of feelings - some of them not even named yet - and experiences, many of them still far from being re-signified. Lesson planning that also considers dialog about feelings as part of the systematic content, either as a pretext or as an in-depth study of the previously listed theme, is in line with the practice of competencies described in the National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC) and in UNESCO's proposal for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

At the beginning of March 2020, we were at school during our collective study time, reflecting on the correspondence between the ESD key competences and the Matriz de Saberes do Currículo da Cidade de São Paulo. That day we read (SÃO PAULO, 2019B, p. 37):

A curriculum designed today needs to dialogue with the dynamics and dilemmas of contemporary society, so that new generations can actively participate in the positive transformation of both their local reality and global challenges.

Well, today the disturbing reality is the favorable state of opportunities for effective work based on this curriculum, enabling the formation "of ethical, responsible and supportive citizens who strengthen a more inclusive, democratic, prosperous and sustainable society" (SÃO PAULO, 2019B, p.35). Self-knowledge and self-care can be experienced through activities, games or dynamics that promote reports of personal impressions and authorial artistic records. Empathy and cooperation are experienced right from respectful listening to the shared narratives, as well as in the construction of the week's study agenda together with the students, providing time for a welcome, a review of what was worked on in the previous meeting,

the development of the day's proposal and

individual and/or collective self-assessment. These proposals are pertinent and attentive to the intention of welcoming, dialogue, systematization of content and health care protocols. Strategies to anticipate the routine can have a mitigating effect on the reactions of students who are suffering from anxiety, their anxieties and insecurities, as well as keeping the channel for dialog open. Proposing a regular routine for certain activities is another possible support for students' internal organization, enabling them to activate their repertoire in advance through the opportunity to research. This form of anticipation also has the potential to reduce anxiety in the class, as it helps personalize the teaching and learning process.

Having the script of the lesson proposal in sight, with objectives, procedures and evaluation criteria known to the whole class, as the dynamics of the lesson are experienced, favors the management of events, since everyone involved in the process is sharing responsibility and is repeatedly led to reflect on their contributions and commitment.

Managing daily life in order to lead to a successful school career, imbuing practices with intentionality, requires the use of strategies that cannot be random or haphazard, given that they reflect a concept of teaching and learning, and the action dynamics of today's young people require an environment where the subject is active, participative and takes responsibility for their journey of building knowledge. Another factor to be considered is the development of proposals that either prioritize working with screens or encourage disconnection from them.

The challenge of remote learning, if on the one hand it has led to a huge portion of society daring to appropriate knowledge from digital technologies, on the other it has deepened the inequalities in access to these same technologies. By the way, looking at the issue of social gulfs and their variables - so cruel as to generate data proving that the coronavirus kills more black and poor people in Brazil and around the world (GRAGNANI, 2020) - could be pertinent content for developing appropriate strategies for exercising critical, systemic and problem-solving thinking.

While it seems unlikely that we will ever return to classes that passively tolerate lessons reduced to blackboards and chalk, the knowledge gained by teachers during this distressing time of precarious remote teaching can be improved through the collaboration of the students themselves. As well as being a promising opportunity to expand knowledge, the inversion in the dynamics of who teaches and who learns nurtures bonds and empathy, reconnecting human contact.

In this context, in the material published with the conclusions of work advised by Telma Weisz (SÃO PAULO, 2018), the profile of investigative teachers is characterized by being based on previous questions and concerns that are fundamental to educational action:

- which objectives are relevant;
- what the class's repertoire of knowledge is;
- what content will be covered;
- when and for how long the activities will take place;
- and what and how to proceed to guarantee learning.

It is in planning that the needs, potential and aspirations of the group of students serve as parameters for adapting the learning objectives and selecting the content needed to achieve them. To this end, planning the work to be carried out in the classroom starts with diagnostic surveys of the students to find out what their previous knowledge is, their potential and what they still need to learn. Once we have identified the class's repertoire of knowledge and listed the objectives to be achieved, we can proceed to systematize the content that should guarantee meaningful learning. In addition, continually making use of the resources that are feasible in terms of the time and space available and rounding off the day's agenda with a moment to appreciate the activities and one's own performance are procedures that make it possible to record information and contribute to the selection of more powerful strategies.

In addition, Weisz (2009) already emphasized the need for teachers to consider the details: • matching the theme to the interests of the class whenever possible;

- how much time will be allocated to learning possibilities at different times in relation to the complexity of the content;
- the contextualization of the lesson with social language practices, based on the relevance and achievement of the selected objectives and content;

- planning in such a way as to allow for the progressive development of the level of autonomy and determination of the class and of each student in particular;

- a curriculum arranged in a spiral, in which the contents are offered in due time, taking into account the potential of the students and the degree of depth differentiated at each sequence of activities, stage or year of the cycle;

- the learning that is possible, within the evaluation criteria, which must refer to the learning that is essential for the continuity of the process;

- promoting organized teaching from the complex to the simple and back to the complex, challenging but not unattainable;

- more explicit systematization of the essential aspects of the content worked on;

- the need for coordination between curricular components and content, with a view to interdisciplinary work whenever possible;

- reviewing activities using strategies, environments (online and face-to-face) and time slots that are relevant to the students' learning process. As for the arrangement of activities, Lerner (2002) describes three organizational modalities, which should be provided in a systematic, routine, intentional and learning-promoting way:

- project work: a sequence of activities culminating in the production of a final product

to be exhibited;

- sequences of activities: tasks to be carried out successively with the intention of leading to the acquisition of specific knowledge and, consequently, to the achievement of the learning objectives set;

- independent activities: isolated activities that can be habitual or occasional.

The criteria that really differentiate them are the frequency and duration involved in the classroom and the potential of each organizational modality for specific content.

As the different organizational modalities can be combined in the development of a single piece of work, once the objectives have been listed, they can be broken down into simpler specific objectives and brought together in such a way that the successive activities proposed to consolidate them give rise to sequences of activities. Breaking down broader objectives into more specific ones is an effective principle for designing sequences of activities that lead to the achievement of that first, broader objective.

Interpreting the achievement of each objective as a succession of phases to be conquered can provide positive feedback on the process that learners are going through to build their knowledge.

Completely adaptable to the use of various digital technologies, the methodological movements of work - collective work, in groups, in pairs and autonomously - together with the organizational modalities favor a more powerful approach to the content and guarantee a more significant quality of learning.

There are methodological movements (SÃO PAULO, 2019b) that enhance the acquisition of certain contents to the detriment of others and the spaces and times to be used need to be prepared in advance. The diversity of groupings not only contributes to learning to work collaboratively, but also helps to acquire the progressive ability to carry out activities independently.

It is possible to associate this work dynamic with the learning styles of the students (MELARÉ; BARROS, 2008), and it is of great value to provide experiences that reconcile methodological work movements and ways of learning according to the personal skills and abilities of each group of students. Approaching the same content in different ways and providing successive approaches to the same content - in a gradually deepening treatment - guarantees the expansion of learning expectations throughout the process.

In the institutional document City Curriculum: Early Childhood Education (2019a), welcoming is defined as both a principle and a working method. If it is experienced permanently in everyday life from the moment we return to face-to-face classes, it will give credibility to the intentional construction of educational work.

Although the seriousness of the situation requires constant rigor in relation to the restrictions imposed by covid-19, students cannot be deprived of an environment that inspires a sense of security and welcome, especially through classroom dynamics permeated by respect, dialogue, listening, cooperation and empathy. The process of rebuilding bonds with the school will certainly take place through opportunities to talk about feelings, past difficulties, traumatic or positive experiences, periods of isolation, meetings in the family environment and returning (CNE, 2020). Good pedagogical practices can be the result of another look at the lessons learned during the period of social distancing, combining attention to the effervescence of contemporaneity with careful systematization of activities, with a view to intentionality. A unique aspect of this tragic event is that it affected all societies in some way, although undeniably to varying degrees. This results in the broad resonance of feelings, impressions and identification not only among the students, but also between them and the teachers, since everyone was immersed in the same historical time of uncertainty and anguish (ALFAGEME, 2020).

Thus, it is up to the teacher to develop appropriate systematization that presupposes a repertoire of content that dialogues with some aspect of the

students' reality, so that, by building connections, they can extrapolate their understanding. Undoubtedly, their experiences, knowledge, potential and difficulties are a rich repertoire of possibilities for approaching curricular content organized according to the objectives to be achieved (SÃO PAULO, 2019c).

As well as analyzing the teaching reports and talking to the teacher and CP, my role as PAP also consisted of sitting next to the children and teenagers to talk about what their difficulties were and how I could help them. They taught me much more through enriching exchanges of experiences and coping strategies, in other words, reciprocal listening and reflection on difficulties and anxieties as strategies for building a repertoire of how to learn how to learn.

Repeated academic training, although relevant, often distances itself from the reality of the classroom floor and promotes reflections that have little impact on practice. As a teacher, I opted for those that provoked me to deconstruct the practices rooted in my daily actions, most of which came from my own student memories.

Although people have beautiful memories of their school days, I am one of those who have discouraging memories of the dynamics of carrying out intramural tasks and, therefore, reframing my career from the point of view of continuing education was the most appropriate starting point. Having been an elementary school student in suburban public schools in the last century, being a black woman and also a teacher in a suburban public school invites me to reflect and intervene, based on the training meetings, committed to education as a right denied to the enslaved black population for centuries, to collaborative collective work between all the social agents in the school community and to the principle of equity, essential aspects for raising the learning expectations of students from working class backgrounds.

Telma Weisz (2009) does not propose condemning the past, but recognizing that responses to contemporary demands are intertwined with this current historical moment - with its conflicting

legacies, technologies, diversities, contradictions and inequalities. This alignment is possible given teacher training that favors a better understanding of educational theories, avoiding dissonance in their adaptation to practice (SÃO PAULO, 2019c). Training in group sessions between teachers to study and identify common and recurring difficulties expands the repertoire of searching for and developing assertive practices in partnership. In order for me to make the most of these moments, it became essential for me to adopt an investigative stance on the difficulties and potential of the students and my own and, at the same time, to take notes on the teaching and learning process to be reflected on in pedagogical meetings, whether with my peers or pedagogical coordination.

Although remote teaching, which was suddenly instituted, has caused distress and discomfort by requiring education professionals to master technologies that until recently were completely unknown to many of us, access to videoconferencing, distance learning courses, digital education platforms, social networks and the Internet of Things (IOT) has provided indispensable knowledge for the environment to be built in face-to-face classes and for recording the course (SALAS, 2020), making this valuable material to be shared in teaching groups to build and improve practices that mobilize knowledge and promote learning.

We are left with a vast world of anxiety, fear and stress. There is no situation in recent human history in which everyone has been threatened at the same time. The impacts of the crisis on the daily life of societies may vary in degree and tone, but in no way can they be underestimated (PASCUAL, 2020).

Managing pain, loss, lack, frustration, impotence, boredom, surprises and joy will need to be done and requires certain learning processes. The school environment (remote and face-to-face) can be a safe, welcoming and powerful space for developing responsibility, participation, empathy and collaboration, skills needed to deal with feelings and expectations of oneself and others, develop viable, inclusive and equitable strategies and reflect on the norms and values that interfere

with people's choices and actions.

Giving due importance to planning involves selecting situations that, when problematized, add meaning that translates into life. The construction of learning by the students themselves, through the exercise of their protagonism, autonomy and determination, takes place in the dialog between teacher and student, where the latter also has an active voice in a multi-way learning process with competent mediation.

In a face-to-face environment, special attention must be paid to looking people in the eye and verbalizing what facial communication will not articulate effectively, if the use of a mask is still necessary. In some dimension the silent also suffer, so it is essential to create specific opportunities to welcome those who still resist getting involved in the proposed activities.

Using the social experiences of the group of students as clues for selecting approaches, content and strategies makes it possible to add meaning to them. Welcoming the vision of the local community into the classroom as a safe starting point enables teaching that is less content-oriented and more focused on comprehensive education (WEISZ, 2009), as well as the use of resources that enable authorial and collaborative production. Drawing up agreements with the class as to what is prudent to delimit is a useful strategy in both remote and face-to-face environments.

By looking and listening to the class, the teacher invests in the quality of the socio-affective environment and, instead of expecting students to behave in a way that is consistent with the prison model (passive between bars) or the factory model (obedient to the sirens), they develop students who are protagonists and co-responsible for their learning.

In this space and time of constructing knowledge that is different from that traditionally considered most relevant, understanding constructive error (WEISZ, 2009) also significantly interferes in the socio-affective environment, since it signals the student's reasoning in relation to that particular activity. Paying special attention to the path

and procedures the student used to reach that conclusion adds importance to the effort they put in and the knowledge they have already shown they have acquired by mobilizing it is recognized and praised.

With a view to fruitful interventions, valuable information is detected when welcoming is used as a method (WEISZ, 2009). Dedication to playing the role of reflective teacher suggests mediation in essence and the permanent search for an understanding of how the student thinks and arrives at a particular line of reasoning. This only becomes feasible thanks to the teacher's training repertoire, which enables them to map the students' knowledge-building trajectory and intervene (via replanning) to enhance the possibilities of overcoming the class's difficulties and expanding their knowledge.

This interdependence between all the people involved in the process at the same historical moment helps to establish productive links and collaborative relationships. The proper organization and distribution of activities enhances the autonomy and co-responsibility of the class in the dynamics of the lesson, just as the evaluation of the process, with clear criteria, and the practice of self-assessment, through frequent activities, intensify this co-responsibility.

Planning involves checking the students' conditions and this action presupposes periodically revisiting the notes documented during the process.

The organizational modalities and the methodological movement of work are powerful allies when harmonized with the nature of the content, learning needs and the use of technological tools according to the objectives and specificity of the content (LERNER, 2002). In other words, the study and analysis of the objectives shows which necessary knowledge must be mobilized in order to design viable activities that make the objectives attainable.

It is suggested that the learning and self-assessment roadmaps be built with the class, listing goals, activity proposals and assessment criteria that

will help to make teaching as personalized and stimulating as possible. They are flexible and carefully designed.

Checking the students' conditions, the repertoire from which they will build other associations and being clear about which way of working enhances learning; these are criteria that need to be shared with the class as a strategy for developing guided reflection, shared responsibility, determination and autonomy in each student (SÃO PAULO, 2019a). Aware that hearing praise can be just as uncomfortable as receiving criticism, ethical teachers cannot shy away from having their performance evaluated reciprocally.

CONCLUSION

In view of the history of exclusion suffered by the working classes - especially women and the black population - the active and obstinate search for all students must be promoted, since the school dropout rate - a ghost always lurking in the reports of the most vulnerable communities - is the educational challenge to be overcome in the post-pandemic world and acting on reality implies developing strategies to deal with contradictions and conflicts, improving means of social participation (Chauí, 2008).

When planning educational activities, it is essential to pay attention to the development of each particular lesson in its details, including and essentially in compliance with health protection protocols, whose routine serves as an instrument that helps organize and distribute teaching actions in time and space for successful learning and health safety for all (CNE, 2020).

Although widely flexible in many aspects, the organization to maximize and coordinate the use of didactic time is a decisive item in the process, since it involves working with activities (SALAS, 2020) to build the knowledge of each individual student, as well as the time needed to take care of the health protocols, welcoming, listening, intervening, evaluating and overcoming difficulties.

In conclusion, by integrating moments of reflection

on the assessment of learning with students into planning, we give them the opportunity to discuss, in a respectful and reflective way, the difficulties, strategies and resources we use to develop skills and build knowledge. In addition, it is the ethical duty of everyone involved in welcoming actions to respect each person's learning processes, experiences of loss and protection protocols so that the educational environment promotes health for all dimensions of the person (CNE, 2020).

REFERENCES

- ALFAGEME, A. A world of anxiety, fear and stress. *El País*, Madrid, 20 APR 2020. Available at: <https://brasil.elpais.com/sociedade/2020-04-20/um-mundo-de-ansiedade-medo-e-estresse.html>. Accessed on: 14 Nov 2020.
- BARROS, V. The theory of learning styles: convergence with digital technologies. *Revista SER: Saber, Educação e Reflexão*. V. 1, nº 2, p. 14-28, 2008. Available at: <https://repositorioaberto.uab.pt/bitstream/10400.2/2999/3/70-228-1-PB%202.pdf>. Accessed on: 20 Nov 2020.
- BRAZIL. Letter of Law of March 25, 1824. Political Constitution of the Empire of Brazil, of March 25, 1824. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/constituicao/constituicao24.htm. Accessed on: 20 Nov 2020.
- BRAZIL. Constitution of the Federative Republic of Brazil: constitutional text promulgated on October 5, 1988, as amended by Constitutional Amendments Nos. 1 to 6/94, Constitutional Amendments Nos. 1/92 to 91/2016 and Legislative Decree No. 186/2008. Brasília: Federal Senate, Coordination of Technical Editions, 2016. Available at: https://www2.senado.leg.br/bdsf/bitstream/handle/id/518231/CF88_Livro_EC91_2016.pdf. Accessed on: 07 Sep 2020.
- BRAZIL. Law No. 9.394, of December 20, 1996. Establishes the guidelines and bases of national education. Brasília, D.O.U., 1996. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/19394.htm. Accessed on: 14 Nov 2020.
- BRAZIL. Law No. 10.639, of January 9, 2003. Amends Law No. 9.394, of December 20, 1996, which establishes the guidelines and bases of national education, to include the theme "Afro-Brazilian History and Culture" in the official curriculum of the Education Network, and makes other provisions. Brasília, D.O.U., 2003. Available at: <http://portal.mec.gov.br/setec/arquivos/pdf/lei10639.pdf>. Accessed on: 20 Nov 2020.
- BRAZIL. National Pact for Literacy at the Right Age: guiding document. Brasília: MEC, 2017. Available at: http://pacto.mec.gov.br/images/pdf/doc_orientador/doc_orientador_versao_final.pdf. Acesso on: 2 Mar 2020.
- BRAZIL. Continuing professional development program: literacy. Brasília: The Secretariat, 1999. Available at: http://portal.mec.gov.br/seb/arquivos/pdf/pcn_acao/pcnacao_alf.pdf. Accessed on: 20 Nov 2020.
- BRAZIL. Literacy Teacher Training Program - PROFA: presentation document. Brasília: MEC, 2001. Available at: <http://portal.mec.gov.br/seb/arquivos/pdf/Profa/apres.pdf>. Accessed on: 20 Nov 2020.
- CHAUÍ, Marilena. Culture and democracy. *Crítica y Emancipación*, (1): 53-76, junio 2008.
- CHAUÍ, Marilena. Political culture and cultural politics. *Estudos avançados*, v. 9, n. 23, p. 71-84, 1995.
- CME. CME Recommendation No. 04, of August 20, 2020. Rules for the return to face-to-face activities/classes in the Educational Units of the Municipal Education System of São Paulo, suspended as a temporary and emergency measure to prevent contagion by COVID-19. 2020. Disponível em: <https://www.sinesp.org.br/179-saiu-no-doc/10515-recomendacao-cme-n-04-2020-normas-para-o-retorno-as-atividades-aulas-presenciais-nas-unidades-educacionais-do-sistema-municipal-de-ensino-de-sao-paulo-suspensas-como-medida-temporaria-e-emergencial-de-prevencao-do-contagio-pelo-covid-19#:~:text=PELO%20>

COVID-19-, RECOME-
NDA%3%87%C3%83O%20CME%20
N%C2%BA%2004%2F2020%20%2D%20
NORMAS%20PARA%20O%20RETORNO%20
%C3%80S, DO%20CONT%3%81GIO%20
PELO%20COVID%2D19. Accessed on: 20 Nov
2020.

GRAGNANI, J. Why coronavirus kills more
black and poor people in Brazil and around
the world. BBC News, London, July 12, 2020.
Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/portuguese/brasil-53338421>. Accessed on: 20 Nov 2020.

LERNER, D. Reading and writing at school:
the real, the possible and the necessary. Porto
Alegre: Artmed, 2002.

NOVA ESCOLA. Pedro Demo talks about
education through research. Nova escola, São
Paulo, 10 Nov 2010. Available at:

[https://novaescola.org.br/conteudo/3881/
pedro-demo-fala-sobre-educacao-pela-pesquisa](https://novaescola.org.br/conteudo/3881/pedro-demo-fala-sobre-educacao-pela-pesquisa).
Accessed on: 14 Nov 2020.

PASCUAL, A. Positive uncertainty, a path
to success. El País, São Paulo, 05 NOV
2020. Available at: [https://brasil.elpais.com/
sociedade/2020-11-05/incerteza-positiva-um-
caminho-ao-sucesso.html](https://brasil.elpais.com/sociedade/2020-11-05/incerteza-positiva-um-caminho-ao-sucesso.html). Accessed on: 14 Nov
2020.

PATTO, Maria Helena Souza. The production
of school failure: a story of submission and
rebellion. 1987.

SALAS, P. Remote learning is not all about
technology: offline strategies expand access to
activities in quarantine. Nova Escola, São Paulo,
July 27, 2020. Available at: [https://novaescola.
org.br/conteudo/19547/nem-so-de-tecnologia-
vive-o-ensino-remoto-estrategias-off-line-
ampliam-acesso-as-atividades-na-quarentena](https://novaescola.org.br/conteudo/19547/nem-so-de-tecnologia-vive-o-ensino-remoto-estrategias-off-line-ampliam-acesso-as-atividades-na-quarentena).
Accessed on: Nov 14, 2020.

SÃO PAULO. City curriculum: Early Childhood
Education. São Paulo: SME/COPED, 2019a.

SÃO PAULO. Currículo da cidade: Ensino

Fundamental: componente curricular: Língua
Portuguesa. São Paulo: SME/COPED, 2019b.

SÃO PAULO. Learning rights in the
interdisciplinary and authorial cycles. São Paulo:
SME/COPED, 2016.

SÃO PAULO. Study Guide for Collective
Working Hours: Subsidies for pedagogical
coordinators. São Paulo: SME/DOT, 2006a.

SÃO PAULO. SME Normative Instruction
No. 34, of November 1, 2019. Provides for the
organization of reading rooms, reading spaces
and reading centers. Available at: [https://www.
sinesp.org.br/179-saiu-no-doc/8928-instrucao-
normativa-sme-n-34-de-01-11-2019-dispoe-
sobre-a-organizacao-das-salas-de-leitura-
espacos-de-leitura-e-nucleos-de-leitura](https://www.sinesp.org.br/179-saiu-no-doc/8928-instrucao-normativa-sme-n-34-de-01-11-2019-dispoe-sobre-a-organizacao-das-salas-de-leitura-espacos-de-leitura-e-nucleos-de-leitura).
Accessed on: November 20, 2020.

SÃO PAULO. Curriculum guidelines: learning
expectations for ethnic-racial education in early
childhood education, primary and secondary
education. São Paulo: SME/DOT, 2008.

SÃO PAULO. Curriculum guidelines and
proposed learning expectations for elementary
school: cycle I. São Paulo: SME/DOT, 2007.

SÃO PAULO. Teaching guidelines for the city's
curriculum: Portuguese language. São Paulo:
SME/COPED, 2019c. v.1.

SÃO PAULO. Referencial de expectativas para
o desenvolvimento da competência leitora e
escritora no ciclo II do ensino fundamental. São
Paulo: SME/DOT, 2006b.

WEISZ, T. The dialog between teaching and
learning. São Paulo: Ática, 2009.